

From formulaic to forms?

Tracing the evolution of speech and information flows in diplomatic letters¹

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Scholars have remarked upon the importance of diplomatic language and the formulaic character of diplomatic correspondence but have paid far less attention to formulaic expressions as a way to detect and explore the communicative functions of diplomatic reporting and trace its transformation over time. We are inspired by information history in general and especially by the research conducted on the Huygens project REPUBLIC concerning the potential of formulaic phrases to identify parts of (administrative) texts and to give access to specific information.² Our paper has a twofold aim. First, it investigates whether formulaic expressions can be used to identify instances of direct speech (quoting someone verbatim) within ambassadorial correspondence from the seventeenth to the twentieth century. Diplomacy was (and still is) conducted primarily through oral exchanges, and historians have noted that their despatches abound with traces of orality but have hitherto not paid any attention to examining both why and how ambassadors tried to capture negotiations and speech on paper.³ Secondly, we explore the development over time of the information flow in diplomatic correspondence by analysing the placement and the change in formulaic elements which introduce topics within the correspondence, to find out if there is an interaction between the way information is communicated and evolving administrative practices. Thus, we strive to

¹ We would like to thank Ida Nijenhuis for her comments on an earlier draft.

² I. Nijenhuis, Analyse van de vroegmoderne politieke taal: retorische structuur en discours (unpublished paper 2012); M. Koolen and R. Hoekstra, *Detecting Formulaic Language Use in Historical Administrative Corpora*. Proceedings of the Computational Humanities Research Conference 2022. Antwerp, Belgium, December 12-14, 2022. https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3290/long_paper5740.pdf (last visited 14-01-2024); M. Koolen, R. Hoekstra, J. Oddens and R.G.H. Sluijter, *Formulas and decision-making: the case of the States General of the Dutch Republic*. Proceedings of the Computational Humanities Research Conference 2023, Paris, France, December 6-8, 2023. https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3290/long_paper5740.pdf (last visited 14-01-2024).

³ See F. De Vivo, 'Archives of Speech: Recording Diplomatic Negotiation in Late Medieval and Early Modern Italy', *European History Quarterly* 46:3 (2016), pp. 519-544.

answer the question of the value of formulaic language as a methodological approach to tracing spoken words and themes in ambassadorial correspondence.

We have chosen a diachronic perspective on serial sources (diplomatic despatches) and in the initial selection of our material we have relied upon our own historical specialism. This means that we will move from early seventeenth-century Venetian diplomacy to Dutch diplomacy in the United States of America during the Second World War. We examine the letters sent by Suriano, the Venetian envoy in The Hague between 1616-1623, to the Venetian Doge and Senate. For the modern era, we use the letters sent by A. Loudon (1892-1953), the Dutch envoy, later ambassador, in Washington between 1942 and 1947 to E.N. van Kleffens (1894-1983), the Dutch minister of Foreign Affairs (1939-1946). We are aware that moving from the seventeenth century to the twentieth century leaves more than two centuries of development unaccounted for, nevertheless, we think the preliminary findings of our paper will offer enough food for thought to study this specific material from a diachronic perspective.

While diplomatic practices after the Congress of Vienna (1814-1815) and the speed of communication changed significantly after the invention of the telegraph, letters (even in handwriting) continued to be exchanged across the Atlantic between Loudon to Van Kleffens during the Second World War. The two used the correspondence to 'catch up' (bij te praten in Dutch) or 'to think out loud, or rather with the pen'. Diplomats were and have remained information managers and knowledge workers and letters were their preferred instrument to report on their activities.⁴ Ambassadorial correspondence thus remains a constant in conducting diplomacy. We have therefore chosen these despatches as the key source for our analysis.

⁴ A. Black and A. Bryant, 'Knowledge management and diplomacy: Reflections on the demise of valedictory despatch in the context of an informational history of the British Diplomatic Service', *First Monday* 16:1 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v16i1.3339>.

We first introduce the related works our analysis has built on and then move to the selection and characteristics of our corpora. In the following sections, we present our findings on both direct speech and information flows. Finally, we evaluate the possible meaning of analyzing formulas in a diachronic approach for understanding the evolution of diplomatic reporting and communication and propose possible routes for further research on the relation between changing information flows in letters and evolving administrative practices.

Related work and methodology

Sociolinguists and literary scholars have studied speech representation in literary texts and historic texts more systematically than historians of diplomacy.⁵ Linguists make a difference between direct reported speech (quoting someone verbatim) and indirect reported speech (summarizing someone). Research is being primarily conducted on English literary texts.⁶ Scholars agree that diplomats turn to the stylistic device of direct speech for various reasons, ranging from emphasizing the authenticity of their information, and stressing one's importance to having political protagonists proclaim their own political agendas.⁷ Ambassadorial correspondence represents an underutilized text genre in examining the functions of reported speech. A curious omission in many ways, as diplomats conducted most of their business orally and had to find ways to capture these oral exchanges on paper in their letters to their governments.

The study of formulaic phrases in diplomatic letters also focuses more on other language areas than Dutch. For this paper, we rely primarily on historical research on English business and official correspondence, especially on Okulska's work on early

⁵ Colette Moore, *Quoting Speech in Early English* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2011); Peter J. Grund, and Terry Walker (eds.), *Speech Representation in the History of English. Topics and Approaches* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2021).

⁶ Mel Evans, *Royal Voices: Language and Power in Tudor England* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020) is the exception in looking at letters.

⁷ P. Hoppenbrouwers, 'Heren di parlementeren. Brabantse diplomatieke bedrijvigheid rond 1400', *Tijdschrift voor geschiedenis* 127:4 (2014), pp. 553-558.

modern diplomatic correspondence.⁸ Formulaic language can be traced back to writing conventions, and in our case, the text type "letter" always has the following text structuring parts: address, opening, body, closing and signature. Sociolinguists agree that opening and closing are often characterized by formulaic language and indicative of the hierarchical relationship between sender and recipient.⁹ For the discourse composition of the body of diplomatic letters, Okulska mentions that these body parts are hybrids, in which narrating and reporting alternate, in either argumentative or descriptive modes. She points out the possibilities of analyzing them by giving examples of so-called resumptive expressions; formulaic-attention getters (which can be intersubjective address forms focusing on the relationship between sender and receiver) and intertextual markers such as quotations or the reporting of speech.

With her examples in mind, we have tried to find usable formulas in our corpora, especially those indicating instances of direct speech in the body. Okulska also observes a diachronic change in the rhetorical structure of English diplomatic correspondence from a "topic delayed" thesis presentation to a "topic first" interaction strategy, where the topic of a letter is shifted to the first sentences instead of later in the body of the text. Although it is common knowledge that all official correspondence nowadays is written on prefabricated templates of letters, we are particularly interested from a more institutional or organizational perspective in how this change in information flow in diplomatic correspondence evolved in the twentieth century. We have tried to find clues for a relationship between the development of efficiency-enhancing letter templates structuring both 'content-related' and administrative processes in an increasingly complex organization like the Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

As the twentieth-century corpus is not digitally available and is much smaller in size than the Surriano corpus (and we both lack expertise in digital/computational analysis), the analysis in this paper is done by analogue close reading. However, in trying to

8 U. Okulska, 'Textual Strategies in the Diplomatic Correspondence of the Middle and Early Modern English Periods: The Narrative Report Letter as a Genre', in M. Dossena & S.M. Fitzmaurice (eds.) *Business and Official Historical Investigations* (Peter Lang AG, EAP, Bern 2006), p. 47-77.

9 Van der Wal, Afscheidscollege.

identify formulaic phrases, we have kept in mind the notes on potential candidate formulas and word n-grams discussed in the above-mentioned papers of Koolen and Hoekstra c.s.

Corpora

The Venetian envoy Suriano was expected to write weekly. The frequency of writing was dictated by the weekly courier services between Venice and Antwerp (the main axe of communication at the time). Depending on the ongoing events, he wrote two letters on the same day, in exceptional circumstances even three on a single day. Upon arrival in Venice, these letters were achieved by secretaries, and his 725 letters written between 1616 and 1623 have been kept together in a single archive series.

The situation in the twentieth century is very different, here we were faced with disturbed record management and several complex (re-)arrangements of ministerial and personal archives during and after the Second World War because of the London exile of the Dutch government. Due to these circumstances, the serial nature of the correspondence is less clear than in the seventeenth century. For this paper, we selected 75 letters (despatches) from three different collections within the archives of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs: 43 letters from the so-called Office-archive Van Kleffens and the work archive Loudon. Van Kleffens' Office-archive consists of a serial correspondence with Loudon. The despatches are about political affairs, some of them having such a secret-official character, that Loudon preferred to write the issues concerned to Van Kleffens personally, instead of putting them in an official report. However, some of these letters can take on a real private character. To be able to compare this with the strictly official letters, we also selected 32 letters from the collection "Political reports America" from the secret archives of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

Analysis: General observations

Concerning the opening /closing of the letters in both corpora, it is crucial to note that these epistolary exchanges did not occur between equals. Ambassadors were reporting to superiors. There was an uneven balance in their relationship, recognizable by phrases such as 'Serene Prince', 'Your Serenity' or 'Your Excellency'. However, in the correspondence kept in the Office-archive Van Kleffens there is a development from a hierarchical to a more equal opening. From 1941 onwards Loudon (also) opens with 'Amice' and closes with '*ut semper*' or '*vale*'. It is also worth noting that both men started sending their greetings to the 'Mrs' but later just to 'Betty' and 'Margaret'.

In both corpora, in the body of the letters text structuring elements can be detected: there is an alternation of narrating and reporting in descriptive or argumentative modes with more or less formulaic attention-getters and address forms. Such as for the 17th century:

- 'Anyway, Most Serene Prince, what I have indicated to you at other times'
- 'With the addition that the matter is greater than I could believe'
- 'Your Serenity has seen that I spoke not without foundation'
- 'I will remain attentive to inform Your Serenity of [...]

And for the 20th century:

- 'It occurs to me that' (*het schijnt mij dat*)
- 'because in my humble opinion' (*omdat naar mijn bescheiden mening*)
- 'it lies far beyond me to wish to argue' (*het ligt mij verre om te willen bepleiten*)
- 'Your Excellency will no doubt agree with me, that [...]' (*Uwe Excellentie zal het ongetwijfeld met mij eens zijn, dat*)

Although they seem to structure the body text, in this stage of our research we are not sure if they can be seen as possible candidate formulas (and for now it's not possible to count their occurrence in both our corpora for several reasons). In addition, they do not provide sufficient guidance to find instances of direct/indirect speech.

Direct/indirect reported speech

Early modern spelling is not standardized and the use of quotation marks to indicate someone is being quoted verbatim is entirely absent in the diplomatic dispatches sent by Suriano. The absence of quotation marks presents researchers with a significant challenge to distinguish direct from indirect speech. Only in rare cases, Suriano added other indications which make it clearer that he is directly quoting, for instance when he reported the following (my own italics to indicate the direct quotes of spoken words):

he said to me with these formal words *here I am ruined entirely, I see no appearance of good for me unless God sends it to me*. Then he added *who knows, perhaps fortune will turn*.

Modern material also presents us with similar challenges. Even in the twentieth century the “ ” are sometimes absent or used for other purposes than just quoting someone speaking. For instance, they are regularly used to present passages from speeches, newspapers and books or to refer to common phrasing.

Based on both our material, we think that combining names of individuals and words that indicate interactions between the ambassador and a third person is a potential route to find speech much more easily (and automatically).

In Suriano's letters looking for Prince Maurice and Suriano's ambassadorial colleagues in combination with verbs related to speaking (in Italian 'disse' which is the past tense of 'dire' or 'rispose', replying/answering) seems a particularly fruitful way to find different speech acts. In the following example, both verbs are captured in a single exchange.

Maurice added *Will he indeed remain in service of will he be dismissed?* I said that [...]. His excellency replied.¹⁰

In a letter dated 24 March 1619, Suriano repeatedly captured Maurice of Nassau's reaction to specific information:

He said *I am very pleased with this news, such a good outcome is commendable, and one must pray to God to converse such unity/union for a long time.*¹¹

Adding that Maurice:

said with a smile *the Republic [of Venice] had declared war on Ferdinand [...]*.¹²

Suriano frequently mentions that Maurice is smiling whilst saying something or answering with a cheerful face (in Italian: *mi rispose con faccia allegra*). Speech acts are often related or close to other bodily expressions in the medieval and early modern period, and therefore may be fruitful to include in digital searches. In several other letters, Suriano reported that his interlocutors either shrugged their shoulders or shrunk their shoulders.¹³

In one of his letters, he added a concluding sentence which offers us more insight into why he captured his conversations.

10 Soggiunse sua Eccellenza bene resterà egli in servitio; o sarà licenziato? io dissi, che per quanto havevo potuto intender non s'era con li suoi capitani ancor voluto accommodar alle condizioni, che se gl'erano offerte; se fosse mo' per farlo non potevo penetrarlo. Rispose sua Eccellenza veramente è difficile lo sminuir la paga ad un soldato, et credo che la serenissima Republica haverà difficoltà grande a superar questo punto.

11 Disse io sono molto ben contento di questa nuova, et laudabile e così buon effetto, et si deve pregar Dio, che si conservi tal unione per longo tempo

12 Et disse sorridendo la Republica per gl'Uscocchi ha rotta la guerra al re | Ferdinando non sarebbe fuori di proposito, ch'ella la rompesse [per] | il medesimo soggetto col re di Spagna.

13 Si strinse nelle spalle, né altro mi rispose; Non seppe rispondermi, si strinse nelle spalle; Solo si restrinse nelle spalle quando sentì parlar del re della Gran Bertagna, et disse che dubitava, che quella Maestà detornasse una sì bella occasione.

Perhaps he said this with some purpose. The prudence of Your Serenity can understand to what extent the intention of this Prince aims. I have nothing else to report but wait here for what will be instructed to.¹⁴

Quoting someone at length and noticing their reactions offered insight into their thought process and figure out their intentions. In another letter, Suriano added the following:

I do not doubt that Your Serenity is informed of his thoughts, but it may be that I serve as a counterpoint.¹⁵

In the seventeenth century, several of these passages were written entirely in cypher and throughout our analysis it became clearer that ciphered parts of the letter were very often related to relaying information about conversations and direct speech. It highlights the importance of speech to understand one's feelings, thoughts and ideas to keep them as hidden as possible from the enemy's interception.¹⁶ And it may be a potential route to detect speech passages using digital tools.

This security aspect is also present in the twentieth-century letters as all these political reports were filed as "safe-files" within the secret archive (only telegrams were in cipher). Words related to speaking or quoting are "I said"; "I discussed"; "I asked" ; "[name third person] still mentioned"; "is it [name third person] wondered..?"; "[name third person] made utterances that could be formulated as".

In the seventeenth and twentieth century some individuals' identities remained hidden, simply being referred to (a) spokesman/spokesmen" (*zagsman/zagslieden*) or a friend. Related words to this kind of indirect speech are for instance: "my spokesman was very

14 Forse disse questo con qualche fine. La prudenza | della Serenità vostra può capire fin dove miri il senso di questo Prin-|cipe. Io non ho che far altro, che aspettar di qua quello | mi sarà aggiunto, et da vostra Serenità li suoi prudentissimi comandamenti.

15 Io non dubito, che vostra Serenità non sia informata de' suoi pensieri; ma può esser che le servi di rancontro, che detto Ambasciator mi disse.

16 It would be a fruitful avenue for further research to be able to quantify how much of recorded speech was in cipher.

reserved in his utterances”; “was reported to me”; “to which he replied”. Even in the correspondence between Loudon and Van Kleffens it is sometimes difficult to distinguish direct from indirect speech. In 1942 Loudon reported that together with Vice Admiral Helfrich he visited President Roosevelt and Under Secretary of State Sumner Welles. They discussed the position of France and Loudon seems to report direct speech from Roosevelt:

The president appeared to be unhappy with the latter plan and asked, how can one talk about a civil French government as long as there is so little unanimity in the French camp.¹⁷

The president then spoke to Helfrich about military matters which, he laughingly said, were not for my ears.

For this passage, it is important to remark that there are no quotation marks, that the first sentence is formulated as a questioning sentence without a question mark and that Roosevelt is cited in Dutch. This differs from the reporting of direct speech when Loudon continued his report with the topics he discussed with Sumner Welles, who is quoted in English with quotation marks:

Toen ik terloops opmerkte dat ik hoopte dat ik na den oorlog niet spoedig in een positie zou komen waarbij ik aan Duitse diplomaten de hand zou moeten geven, zeide de heer Welles: “I think it will be long time before Germany can again be admitted within the family of nations.”¹⁸

17 De president bleek met het laatste plan weinig ingenomen te zijn en vroeg, hoe kan men praten over een civiele Fransche regering zolang er in het Franse kamp nog zoo weinig eensgezindheid bestaat.

18 When I remarked in passing that I hoped that after the war I would not soon find myself in a position where I would have to shake hands with German diplomats, Mr Welles said, " I think it will be a long time before Germany can again be admitted within the family of nations."

As this letter was not handwritten, but only signed by Loudon, we cannot be sure if this is (partly) caused by him dictating this letter, which can explain the missing marks, but not the difference in language use.

Van Kleffens' handwritten letter to Loudon on the hot issue of the postwar expulsion of Nazis from the Netherlands in which he quotes Queen Wilhelmina was also for his 'eyes only'. He explains in a ciphered telegram he sent before and not only performs Wilhelmina speaking but also does not deprive Loudon of his own sigh:

My telegram about the undesirability of public discussion of the question of whether or not to deport Nazis and other Krauts is connected with a probable temporary idiosyncrasy of Her Majesty, who simply wants to banish all Nazis ("of course with women and children, you see"); " You will take care of that, then".
 Yep, Yep, after all it is so real thought and so simple in execution.¹⁹

In summary, the formulaic attention-getters in the bodies of the letters do not suffice to find instances of direct speech. We propose – in the case of a digital approach – to combine them with search strings of a combination of performative words/verbs (or numbers) and name(lists) of historical actors relevant to the research topic.

Information flow

When analyzing our corpora for information flow and a possible development from a topic delayed to a topic first presentation, the twentieth-century corpus revealed major differences between the most private letters and the more official in tone (while both types were found in all three collections). In the more private (handwritten) letters we cannot discern an evolution to a topic-first presentation. Both Loudon and Van Kleffens

¹⁹ Mijn telegram over de onwenselijkheid van openbare bespreking van het vraagstuk der al- of niet verbanning van Nazis en andere rotmoffen hangt samen met een waarschijnlijke tijdelijke idiosyncrasie van Hare Majesteit die alle Nazis("natuurlijk met vrouwen en kinderen ziet u") doodeenvoudig wil verbannen; " U wil daar dus wel voor zorgen". Jawel, Jawel, het is immers zo reeel gedacht en zo simpel van uitvoering.

cut across a multitude of topics in these letters that are hardly, if at all, discoverable through formulaic elements. In fact, Van Kleffens sometimes put text brackets around sections in Loudons letters that were politically so important that they were transcribed and added to the secret archive. Even for the 17th-century corpus, it is difficult to tell whether we can speak of a topic-delayed presentation.

The more official letters from Loudon in the Office Archive Van Kleffens show a registration mark and an underlined topic line in the upper left corner, for instance: GA-1223/661 (meaning: Secret Archive_ letter number 1223/661) and: Information Netherlands in the US. The salutation is always followed by an opening. This can refer to attachments or previously sent letters and – when found in the secret archive – the hierarchical relationship most of the time is more explicit (Your Excellency instead of Amice).

However, our selection from the secret archive also contains series of ‘political reports America’ filed on specific topics. These despatches have the same registration marks and underlined topic lines but are almost unrecognizable as the genre “letters”. They are addressed to His Excellency the Minister of Foreign Affairs E.N. van Kleffens (corner left) and they are signed by Loudon himself, but they lack a salutation, and opening and closing sentences. The body can be very lengthy but is always focused on the topic mentioned in the topic line and mostly refers to the clippings from newspapers or articles attached. Furthermore, on the last page (left under) they mention the fact that copies ‘circulated’, thus were sent to other Dutch ambassadorial posts.

The underlined topic line could be interpreted as the utmost form of diachronic change to a topic first presentation, but comparing both our corpora brings us to another conclusion. In early modern Italian diplomatic correspondence from the sixteenth century onwards, it became standard practice to add a separate sheet of news (known as *avvisi*). These handwritten news-sheets were an innovation at the time: completely devoid of salutation, signatures, opening and closing sentences. By the seventeenth century, with each letter separate sheets of news were to be dispatched. Failure on the

part of papal representatives to send these news reports would always result in reminders and fierce reprimands. In 1639, the papal curia even established guidelines for their representatives on how news was to be gathered and noted for political reports. For instance, if there was no news coming from a specific place, that was to be noted: "nothing new from X" or "no letter arrived from X". Information which was not verifiable had to be noted in following way to indicate their speculative nature (their unreliable status) 'they say', 'here it is being said'. The papal representative and his secretaries were specifically told to not discuss but merely to inform ('non discorrere ma puramente avvisare') adding that they had to avoid discussions, urging them to confine oneself to purely informing, even though many ministers of more diligent princes did the opposite. Although early modern historiography defines *avvisi* as the predecessor of printed newspapers in the seventeenth century, we argue that - given the continuity of this kind of political reporting – the explanation of the other shape of these despatches must be sought in regulations (and efficiency-enhancing) practices of the chancery or department.

This interaction between expanding bureaucratic organizations and the ambassadors can also be found after 1945. Apart from protocol we also have indications that record management increasingly comes to define the inner and outer form of *depeches*, as can be seen from the following example. In 1946 Loudon received a letter from the newly established Department Foreign Service within the reorganized Ministry of Foreign Affairs urging him

“not to cover multiple topics in a letter in the future. Since the topics often belong to different departments, dealing with multiple topics in one letter can lead to confusion.”

Three years later that same Department Foreign Service issued three paper templates for three kinds of standard letters to use in future correspondence.

Concluding Remarks

To conclude, formulaic expressions are present in our diplomatic letters, but in this stage of our research more possible candidate formulas have to be found, analysed for their exact meaning and tested to trace the instances of direct speech we were looking for. We do see a few ways in which the initial results can be expanded upon. The next step is to use digital means. Based on our material, we propose that a fruitful way to approach this is 1) looking at a specific actor in combination with a verb related to speaking and 2) using ciphered passages (especially for the early modern period). We want to stress that studying information flows in official letters should always be combined with studying bureaucratic practices and the history of record management. Looking at this material purely from a linguistic perspective offers too general conclusions and runs the risk of glancing over the specific nature of the material. The follow-up question should be whether and if so in what ways the regulations and administrative templates ultimately affect the provision of information.

Looking at these formulaic expressions was a fruitful exercise and learning experience for us both. It has allowed us to approach the material in new ways and to trace the developments of chancery practices. Therefore, we are convinced that using formulaic expression provides fruitful avenues for a variety of historians. To give just one example to conclude, it may offer a new way to find information in the text to reconstruct the network of a diplomat much more quickly. It allows us to know with whom they interacted and exchanged information or at least whom they wanted their superior to know they were interacting with. It is also here that we see quite a lot of potential for a more gendered history of diplomacy given the fact that from our small twentieth-century corpus the wives of both Loudon and Van Kleffens played a role in maintaining their networks as more recent studies already argued.²⁰

²⁰ See S. Erlandson, "Off the record: Margart van Kleffens and the gendered history of Dutch World War II diplomacy, (2019) <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616742.2018.1528877>